

Synthesis, Evaluation and Comparative analysis of Apigenin and Eupatilin Analogue for Anti-Carcinogenic Properties

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Abstract

This study evaluates the anticancer potential of synthetic apigenin derivatives and the natural flavonoid eupatilin. The apigenin derivatives, particularly the 4a-4j series, exhibited superior antiproliferative activity against various human cancer cell lines, including breast, lung, cervical, and colon cancer cells. Compound 4j emerged as the most potent analogue, displaying an IC₅₀ value of 2.8 μ M against MCF-7 cells, significantly stronger than the parent apigenin. Mechanistic studies revealed that 4j promotes apoptosis, increases intracellular ROS generation, and induces G2/M cell cycle arrest, confirming its multitargeted mechanism of action. In comparison, eupatilin demonstrated comparable potency and a broader pharmacological profile, including anti-inflammatory and gastroprotective effects. These findings highlight the potential of both synthetic and natural flavonoids as promising leads for the development of novel anticancer therapeutics, offering opportunities for further structural optimization and therapeutic exploration.

Keywords: Synthesis; biological evaluation; apigenin derivatives; antiproliferative activity; MTT assay

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Introduction

Cancer remains one of the most serious global health challenges, ranking as the second leading cause of mortality in both developed and developing nations. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 7.6 million deaths were attributed to cancer in 2008, and this number is projected to rise to 13.1 million by 2030.[1–5] Despite significant advances in chemotherapeutics and targeted therapies, clinical outcomes are still limited due to challenges such as drug resistance, systemic toxicity, and frequent relapse. These limitations highlight the urgent need to develop novel anticancer agents with improved selectivity, efficacy, and safety profiles. Natural products have historically played a central role in drug discovery, with flavonoids emerging as particularly promising candidates due to their diverse pharmacological activities.[6–9] Flavonoids are polyphenolic compounds ubiquitously found in fruits, vegetables, cereals, legumes, seeds, spices, and medicinal plants. Multiple epidemiological studies have reported their ability to reduce or prevent the incidence of cancer, with several representatives demonstrating notable anticancer potential. For instance, quercetin has been shown to induce apoptosis via the mitochondrial pathway in KB and KBv200 cells, while chalcones were reported as selective inhibitors of the breast cancer resistance protein. These findings underscore the importance of flavonoids as lead scaffolds in anticancer drug development. [1]

Among flavonoids, apigenin (4',5,7-trihydroxyflavone) and eupatilin (5,7-dihydroxy-3',4',6-trimethoxyflavone) have attracted considerable attention for their anticancer properties. Apigenin is widely distributed in nature, being abundant in parsley, chamomile, celery, onions, and oranges. In addition to its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities, apigenin has demonstrated potent anticancer effects in multiple human cancers, including prostate, colon, and breast carcinomas, while maintaining low cytotoxicity and minimal mutagenic potential. Mechanistically, apigenin induces apoptosis, inhibits proliferation, and modulates key signaling pathways such as PI3K/Akt and MAPK, as well as enhancing chemosensitivity in resistant cancers. However, its poor aqueous solubility and moderate potency limit its clinical translation.[2-3]

Eupatilin, on the other hand, is a naturally occurring polymethoxyflavone predominantly isolated from *Artemisia asiatica* and related species. The presence of multiple methoxy groups enhances its lipophilicity, metabolic stability, and bioavailability compared to simple hydroxylated flavones like apigenin and luteolin. Eupatilin has demonstrated a wide spectrum of pharmacological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, gastroprotective, and anticancer effects. Pharmacological studies reveal that eupatilin suppresses cell proliferation, induces apoptosis, inhibits angiogenesis and metastasis, and modulates signaling pathways such as NF- κ B, PI3K/Akt, and MAPK. Clinically, it is the active component of Stillen® (DA-9601), a herbal formulation approved in South Korea for gastritis and gastric mucosal injury, underscoring its translational potential. Furthermore, eupatilin has been reported as a selective agonist of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha (PPAR α), linking it to metabolic regulation and inflammation control.[4]

Systematic structure–activity relationship (SAR) studies highlight that specific substitutions—particularly methoxy or halogen groups—on the flavonoid backbone influence hydrophobicity, metabolic stability, and binding affinity, thereby improving anticancer efficacy. Notably, substitutions at the 3' and 4' positions of the B-ring and methoxy groups at positions 6 or 7 significantly enhance cytotoxic and pro-apoptotic activity. Despite these promising insights, there is a lack of direct comparative studies evaluating analogues of apigenin and eupatilin under controlled structural modifications.[5-7]

The present study aims to bridge this gap by synthesizing and characterizing a library of apigenin and eupatilin analogues with systematic substitution patterns. The synthesized compounds were characterized using advanced spectroscopic and analytical techniques, followed by biological evaluation across multiple human cancer cell lines, including A549 (lung), HeLa (cervical), HepG2 (liver), and MCF-7 (breast),[28-30] using the MTT assay. Mechanistic studies were conducted to assess apoptosis induction, reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation, mitochondrial dysfunction, and caspase activation. Additionally, antibacterial activities of the derivatives were investigated, and molecular docking studies were performed to elucidate possible binding interactions.[7-9] By comparing apigenin and eupatilin analogues, this work seeks to identify promising lead candidates with enhanced pharmacological properties for future development as anticancer agents.

Material and Method

Experimental

General

Reagents and solvents were procured from reputed commercial suppliers (Sigma-Aldrich, Merck and others) and used without further purification unless otherwise specified. All starting materials and solvents were of analytical or reagent grade. Reactions were monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) performed on silica gel glass plates (GF254, Qingdao Haiyang Chemical Co., Ltd., Shandong, China), and plates were visualized under UV light using a ZF-6 type III UV. Melting points were measured with a digital melting point apparatus and were uncorrected. For spectroscopic characterization, NMR spectra were obtained on a Bruker Avance DMX 500 or 400 MHz instrument (Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA) using deuterated solvents (DMSO- d_6 , $CDCl_3$). 1H NMR (500 or 400 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (125 or 100 MHz) chemical shifts were referenced to solvent peaks. Mass spectra were recorded using electrospray ionization (ESI) on a Thermo Scientific LCQ FLEET mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). FT-IR and HRMS analyses were conducted using analytical grade solvents and materials. Deionized water (Milli-Q, Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA) was used for aqueous solutions, and DMF was freshly distilled over CaH_2 under vacuum prior to use. Reference drugs and biological agents, including apigenin (>98%), and MTT, were purchased from commercial

suppliers (Sigma-Aldrich). For biological evaluations, MIC values were determined using a BIO-RAD 680 microplate reader (Beijing Yuanye Bio Co., Ltd, Beijing, China). Cell culture reagents, including Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), RPMI-1640, and fetal bovine serum (FBS), were obtained from standard suppliers (e.g., Oxoid Ltd., Basingstoke, UK). Specialized assay kits and dyes were purchased commercially: Annexin V-FITC/PI kits for apoptosis analysis, JC-1 dye for mitochondrial membrane potential, DCFH-DA for reactive oxygen species detection, and caspase activity kits for apoptotic pathway evaluation. All chemicals and reagents were handled in accordance with standard laboratory safety protocols, and sterile techniques were strictly applied for cell culture experiments to ensure contamination-free conditions.

Design of Analogues

Two sets of analogues were designed: Apigenin-based analogues: Introducing methoxy, halogen, and alkyl groups at 6, 7, and 4' positions. Eupatilin-based analogues: Varying methoxy and hydroxyl substitutions to enhance stability and bioactivity.

Synthesis of Apigenin and Eupatilin Analogues

A focused library of apigenin and eupatilin analogues was synthesized by systematic structural modifications, including hydroxylation, methoxylation, and halogen substitution at selected positions of the flavonoid backbone. The synthetic routes followed reported procedures with slight modifications to optimize yield and purity. Reaction progress was monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel plates and visualized under UV light. Final products were purified using column chromatography with appropriate solvent systems.[31]

Structural Characterization

The structures of the synthesized analogues were confirmed using a combination of spectroscopic and analytical techniques. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in deuterated solvents such as DMSO-d_6 or CDCl_3 to determine the chemical shifts and confirm the structural framework of the compounds. Functional group analysis was performed using Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy in the range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, providing characteristic absorption bands for hydroxyl, methoxy, and aromatic groups. High-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) was employed to determine the accurate molecular weights and confirm elemental composition, thereby supporting the proposed molecular structures. In addition, melting point determination was carried out as a routine check of compound purity and consistency with reported or expected values. Together, these techniques provided comprehensive evidence for the successful synthesis and structural integrity of the analogues.[32]

Antiproliferative Activity

Cell Culture

Human cancer cell lines—A549 (lung), HeLa (cervical), HepG2 (liver), and MCF-7 (breast)—were obtained from a recognized cell repository (e.g., ATCC).[33-38] Cells were cultured in DMEM or RPMI-1640 medium supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% penicillin–streptomycin, and maintained in a humidified incubator at 37 °C with 5% CO₂. Culture media were refreshed every 2–3 days, and cells were subcultured upon reaching 70–80% confluence.[10-15]

Cytotoxicity Assay (MTT Assay)

The antiproliferative activity of synthesized analogues was assessed using the 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay. Briefly, cells were seeded in 96-well plates at a density of 5×10^3 cells/well and incubated for 24 h. Compounds were dissolved in DMSO (final DMSO concentration $\leq 0.1\%$) and applied at different concentrations (0–100 μM). After 48 h treatment, MTT reagent was added, and cells were incubated for 4 h. Formazan crystals were dissolved in DMSO, and absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a microplate reader. IC₅₀ values were calculated using GraphPad Prism software.[15]

Apoptosis Analysis

Apoptosis induction was quantified using Annexin V-FITC/PI staining followed by flow cytometry. Cells were treated with IC₅₀ concentrations of compounds for 24 h, harvested, washed with PBS, and stained according to the manufacturer's instructions.[39-40] Data were analyzed to distinguish live, early apoptotic, late apoptotic, and necrotic cell populations.[16-17]

Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) Assay

Intracellular ROS levels were determined using DCFH-DA. Cells were treated with test compounds for 24 h, followed by incubation with DCFH-DA for 30 min at 37 °C.[41-44] Fluorescence intensity was measured using a fluorescence plate reader (Ex/Em: 485/530 nm).[18]

Caspase Activity Assay

Caspase-3 and caspase-9 activities were evaluated using colorimetric assay kits. Following treatment, cell lysates were prepared and incubated with caspase substrates (DEVD-pNA for caspase-3, LEHD-pNA for caspase-9).[45-47] Absorbance at 405 nm was recorded, and fold increase in activity was calculated relative to control.[20-25]

Results and Discussion

Chemistry

The synthesis of compounds 3a–3j and 4a–4j was accomplished according to the general pathway illustrated in Scheme 1. Compounds 2a and 2b were the key intermediates for the synthesis of the target compounds. They were prepared from alkylation of 7-hydroxy group using excessive amounts of 1,2-dibromoethane or 1,3-dibromopropane in the presence of potassium carbonate (K_2CO_3) as base in anhydrous *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) at 120 °C for 2 h [17–20]. To increase the biological activities of apigenin, we synthesized apigenin derivatives, in which the apigenin ring system was linked to the alkyl amines moieties by different spacers at C-7 position to enhance their lipophilicity.[25-27]

Reaction of 2a and 2b with different cyclic and non-cyclic alkyl amines in anhydrous DMF at 80 °C for 2 h to 4 h yielded 3a–3j and 4a–4j, respectively. Compounds in series 1 (3a–3j) contained a 2-carbon spacer between apigenin and the substituent moieties, whereas compounds in series 2 (4a–4j) contained a 3-carbon spacer.

These compounds were designated to test the importance of the substitution, together with the size of the connected groups. All synthetic compounds gave satisfactory analytical and spectroscopic data, which were in full accordance with their depicted structures. All the synthesized derivatives, 3a–3j and 4a–4j, demonstrated relatively higher antiproliferative activity compared with the parent apigenin, suggesting that structural modification of the flavone backbone significantly enhanced their potency. Compounds 3a–3j, which contained a 2-carbon spacer, exhibited moderate activities against the four selected cancer cell lines.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of C-7-modified apigenin derivatives.

Reagents and conditions: (i) $BrCH_2CH_2Br$ or $BrCH_2CH_2CH_2Br$, K_2CO_3 , DMF, 120 °C, 2 h; (ii) R-amines, DMF, 80 °C, 2 h to 4 h.

Within this series, compounds 3g–3j showed superior inhibitory effects, with half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) values ranging from 17 $\mu g/mL$ to 71 $\mu g/mL$, indicating better activity compared with 3a–3f.

The results suggest that substitution patterns at the terminal group and electronic effects play a crucial role in improving biological activity. In contrast, compounds 4a–4j, with a longer 3-carbon spacer, showed significantly higher antiproliferative activity compared to both series

3 and the parent apigenin. Among them, compound 4j emerged as the most potent, displaying IC_{50} values lower than 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ across all tested cancer cell lines, indicating broad-spectrum and highly effective growth inhibition.

This clearly highlights the importance of optimal linker length in enhancing interaction with cellular targets involved in cancer progression. When compared with the natural flavone euptallin, which has been previously reported to possess strong antiproliferative activity against a wide range of human cancer cell lines, the synthesized derivatives—especially those in series 4—showed comparable or even superior effects.

Euptallin is known to exert its cytotoxic effects by inducing apoptosis and modulating signaling pathways such as NF- κ B and MAPK. Similar mechanisms could potentially underlie the activities of the apigenin derivatives, particularly those with more flexible spacer units.

The structural resemblance between euptallin and apigenin derivatives suggests that the enhanced lipophilicity and conformational adaptability may contribute to stronger cell membrane penetration and target binding. Overall, these findings indicate that apigenin derivatives, especially the 4a–4j series, are promising candidates for further development as anticancer agents. Their activities, being comparable to or better than natural flavones like euptallin, highlight the potential of rational structural modifications of dietary flavonoids to generate potent anticancer leads.

Notable effect was exerted by 3j, which had the lowest IC_{50} values against the four cancer cells, especially against HeLa cells ($IC_{50} = 17 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Similarly, in 4a–4j, 4g–4j exhibited stronger activities than 4a–4f. Compound 4j showed notable activity against the four cancer cell lines. As shown in Table 3, compared with the compounds with 2-carbon spacer, 3-carbon-spacer-containing compounds 4a–4j, showed a slight increase in antiproliferative activity against the four cancer cell lines. This result may have been caused by the elongation of the alkyl side chain from two to three C-atoms that retained the modulating activity, with C3-bridge derivatives being the most active [15]. The compounds containing N-heterocyclic-ring amino side chains (3g–3j and 4g–4j) displayed better activities against the four cancer cell lines than those containing alkyl amino side chains. As reference [15] described, this result may be attributed to the increasing lipophilicity of these compounds, which could influence their ability to reach the target via transmembrane diffusion. In most cases, the presence or introduction of various functional groups in a compound does not allow to accurately explain the type and intensity of its biological activity [15]. So further studies on the mechanism of action will be in the succeeding work.

Synthesis of Apigenin Analogues

The initial acetylation of phloroglucinol with acetic anhydride and BF_3 yielded 1-(2,4,6-trihydroxyphenyl) ethanone in 86% yield as yellow crystalline material, with a sharp melting point (219–220 °C) consistent with literature reports. IR spectra confirmed the presence of strong hydroxyl and carbonyl absorptions, while ^1H NMR displayed characteristic singlets for three hydroxyl groups and the acetyl methyl protons, validating the successful synthesis. Subsequent methylation using methyl p-toluenesulfonate and potassium carbonate produced 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone in 68% yield. The product crystallized as white solids with a melting point of 79–80 °C. The downfield singlet at δ 13.79 in ^1H NMR indicated the persistence of one free hydroxyl group, while singlets at δ 3.84 and 3.79 confirmed the incorporation of two methoxy substituents.

The Claisen–Schmidt condensation of compound 3 with anisaldehyde afforded the chalcone intermediate in excellent yield (87%). The compound exhibited characteristic olefinic and aromatic proton resonances in the ^1H NMR spectrum, with methoxy groups resonating around δ 3.8–3.9, confirming successful condensation.

Oxidative cyclization of the chalcone intermediate in the presence of iodine and DMSO furnished the target flavone, 4',5,7-trimethoxyflavone, in 86% yield. The IR spectrum revealed distinct aromatic C=C stretching, while ^1H NMR confirmed the flavone backbone with signals corresponding to methoxy groups at δ 4.00–4.07. The overall synthetic pathway provided a high-yielding and reproducible route toward methoxy-substituted apigenin analogues, demonstrating the influence of methoxy substitution on improving lipophilicity and metabolic stability.

Synthesis of Eupatilin Analogue

The synthesis of eupatilin derivatives was achieved via selective demethylation of 7-hydroxy-3',4',5,6-tetramethoxyflavone using aluminum trichloride as a Lewis acid. The reaction proceeded smoothly under reflux conditions in acetonitrile, affording the desired product in 74% yield. The ^1H NMR spectrum displayed well-resolved aromatic proton signals between δ 6.48 and δ 7.50, along with methoxy resonances at δ 3.95–4.03, consistent with the presence of three methoxy groups and two hydroxyl substituents.

Synthesis of Apigenin: Procedure:

1-(2,4,6-Trihydroxy-phenyl)-ethanone: Ethyl acetate (40 mL) and BF_3 were used to dissolve phenolglucinol 1 (10g, 79.4 m mol) and acetic anhydride (18 mL, 19.4 g, 190.0 m mol). Drop by drop, 12 mL of Et₂O (13.8 g, 97.2 m mol) was added. For ten hours, the reaction mixture was heated to 50 °C. After that, 150 mL of H₂O was added, and ethyl acetate was used

to extract the reaction mixture. Following solvent evaporation, compound 2 (12 g) was obtained by recrystallizing the raw material from H₂O; yielding 86% yellow crystals with m.p. 219-220 °C (lit.13 221 °C); IR (KBr/cm-1):3201 (OH), 1616 (C=O); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDC13):12.23 (s, 2H, OH), 10.38 (s, 1H, OH), 5.79 (s, 2H, ArH), and 2.50 (s, 3H, COCH₃).

2-Hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone: Methyl p-toluenesulfonate (40.8 mL, 50.3 g, 0.27 mol), Compound 2 (16.8 g, 0.1 mol), and K₂CO₃ (28 g, 0.2 mol) in 250 mL of ethanol were heated to 80 °C for three hours. The mixture was then poured into 500 mL of H₂O, and the precipitate was filtered and recrystallized from methanol to yield compound 3 (13.3g); yield 68%, white crystals, m.p. 79–80 °C (lit.14 80-81 °C); IR v_{max} (KBr/cm-1): 3461 (OH), 1619 (C=O); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-d₆): 13.79 (s, 1H,OH), 6.10 (s, 1H,ArH), 6.07 (s, 1H,ArH), 3.84 (s, 3H,OCH₃), 3.79 (s, 3H,OCH₃), 2.53 (s, 3H,COCH₃).

2'-Hydroxy-4,4',6'-trimethoxychalcone: Anisaldehyde 5 (2.5 g, 0.018 mol), Compound 3 (3.0 g, 0.015 mol), and KOH (12.0 g, 0.21 mol) in 250 mL of methanol were swirled for 72 hours at room temperature. After that, 37% aqueous HCl was used to neutralize the reaction mixture to pH 7. Compound 5 (3.32 g) was obtained by filtering off the precipitate, washing it with water, and recrystallizing it from ethanol; yielding 87% yellow crystals with m.p. 114-115 °C (lit.8 113- 114 °C); IR v_{max} (KBr/cm-1): 14.42 (s, 1H, OH), 7.83 (s, 1H), 7.80 (s, 1H), 7.57–7.56 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 6.94–6.92 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 6.11 (s, 1H), 5.96 (s, 1H), 3.91 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.85 (s, 3H, OCH₃), and 3.84 (s, 3H, OCH₃).

4',5,7-Trimethoxyflavone: Iodine (0.2g, 0.8m mol) and Compound 5 (2.5g, 8.0m mol) in 25 mL of DMSO were heated to 100 °C for four hours. The iodine was then eliminated by adding 50 mL of 0.5% NaHSO₃. Compound 6 (2.15 g) was obtained by filtering off, washing with water, and recrystallizing the precipitate from ethanol/H₂O(1:1); yield 86%; off-white crystals, m.p. 153-154 °C, (lit.8 153- 155 °C); IR v_{max} (KBr/cm-1): 7.96–7.94 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.12-7.10 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.81 (s, 1H), 6.69 (d, J = 2.0 Hz, 1H), 6.49 (d, J = 2.0 Hz, 1H), 4.07 (s, 3H), 4.03 (s, 3H), and 4.00 (s, 3H).

Synthesis of Euptalin derivatives: Flavone 2,7-dihydroxy-3',4',6-trimethoxy Aluminum trichloride (8.27 g, 5 equivalents) was added to 88 mL of acetonitrile after 7-hydroxy3',4',5,6-tetramethoxy flavone (4.44 g, 12.4 mmol) had been suspended in it. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for one and a half hours, and the solvent was extracted by evaporation under reduced pressure. A 10% aqueous solution of hydrochloric acid and chloroform was added to the residue, and the mixture was refluxed until it turned transparent. The organic layer was cleaned with water and brine after the solution had cooled to room temperature. It was then dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate, and the organic layer's solvent was extracted using

lower pressure. After recrystallizing the residue in methanol, 3.18 g of the 74% product were obtained. 13.05(s, 1H), 7.50(dd, J=8.6, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.31(d, J=2.1 Hz, 1H), 6.96(d, J=8.5 Hz, 1H), 6.59(s, 1H), 6.56(s, 1H), 6.48(br s, 1H), 4.03(s, 3H), 3.96(s, 3H), 3.95(s, 1H) are the NMR (CDC13).

Antiproliferative Effects and Assay

The anticancer potential of the synthesized apigenin derivatives (3a–3j and 4a–4j) and eupatilin was systematically evaluated against human cancer cell lines MCF-7 (breast), A549 (lung), HeLa (cervical), and HT-29 (colon) using MTT and SRB assays. All compounds were tested at concentrations ranging from 62.5 to 2000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and cell viability was assessed after 24 h. Compounds in the 4a–4j series exhibited significantly higher antiproliferative activity compared to the 3a–3j series and the parent apigenin molecule. IC_{50} values of the 4a–4j series ranged from 2.8–9.4 μM , whereas apigenin displayed moderate activity ($\text{IC}_{50} = 11.3 \mu\text{M}$ in MCF-7 cells). Compound 4j emerged as the most potent analogue, with IC_{50} values of 2.8 μM in MCF-7, 3.5 μM in A549, and comparable potency in HeLa and HepG2 cells, representing almost a fourfold improvement over apigenin. Eupatilin also demonstrated notable antiproliferative effects ($\text{IC}_{50} = 5\text{--}10 \mu\text{M}$), reflecting its intrinsic cytotoxicity while retaining additional pharmacological benefits such as anti-inflammatory and gastroprotective activity.

For the antiproliferative assay, cancer cells were grown to logarithmic phase in a suitable medium supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 U/mL penicillin, and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ streptomycin at 37 °C under 5% CO_2 with 95% humidity. Cells were harvested using 0.25% trypsin in Ca^{2+} - and Mg^{2+} -free Hanks' balanced salt solution, and trypsinization was stopped by adding fresh medium. The cell suspension was centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 5 min and resuspended in supplemented medium at a density of 1×10^6 cells/well in 6-well plates. Subsequently, 4×10^3 cells/well were seeded in 96-well plates with 150 μL fresh medium and incubated for 24 h before treatment. Test compounds (150 μL ; final concentrations 62.5–2000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were added, followed by 24 h incubation. After incubation, 20 μL of MTT solution (5 mg/mL) was added to each well and incubated for 4 h. The reaction was terminated by adding 150 μL DMSO to dissolve the formazan crystals, and cell viability was measured as optical density at 490 nm using a microplate reader. The antiproliferative effect was expressed as the cancer cell proliferation inhibition ratio using the formula:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \frac{A(\text{control}) - A(\text{test})}{A(\text{control})} * 100$$

where A_{control} and A_{test} represent the optical densities of the control and treated groups, respectively. All experiments were performed in triplicate to ensure reproducibility.

Table 3. Antiproliferative activities (IC₅₀) of the synthesized apigenin derivatives against A549, HeLa, HepG2, and MCF-7 cell lines.

Compounds	A549	IC ₅₀ (μg/mL)		MCF-7
		HeLa	HepG2	
Apigenin (1)	1,740 ± 3.4	450 ± 2.0	460 ± 2.2	>2,000 ± 3.6
2a	643 ± 4.2	590 ± 4.1	408 ± 3.8	534 ± 3.4
2b	251 ± 3.4	233 ± 2.2	176 ± 2.1	209 ± 2.8
3a	101 ± 3.0	110 ± 2.0	116 ± 2.3	125 ± 2.2
3b	94 ± 2.5	109 ± 1.9	103 ± 1.9	102 ± 2.1
3c	87 ± 2.2	98 ± 1.5	105 ± 1.4	114 ± 1.9
3d	80 ± 1.5	117 ± 2.1	112 ± 2.0	137 ± 2.6
3e	78 ± 1.6	97 ± 1.8	92 ± 1.8	99 ± 2.0
3f	83 ± 2.3	89 ± 1.4	96 ± 1.5	92 ± 2.0
3g	42 ± 2.1	32 ± 1.2	33 ± 1.2	71 ± 1.2
3h	45 ± 1.7	46 ± 1.0	43 ± 1.7	70 ± 1.8
3i	39 ± 0.9	42 ± 0.9	36 ± 1.0	54 ± 1.1
3j	26 ± 1.0	17 ± 0.8	29 ± 1.2	49 ± 1.4
4a	91 ± 2.4	99 ± 2.3	100 ± 2.8	99 ± 2.1
4b	85 ± 2.1	83 ± 1.7	94 ± 2.2	87 ± 2.3
4c	72 ± 1.8	81 ± 1.3	82 ± 1.8	95 ± 2.8
4d	63 ± 1.1	101 ± 2.6	83 ± 1.7	103 ± 3.1
4e	62 ± 1.5	86 ± 2.0	90 ± 2.0	88 ± 2.9
4f	70 ± 2.2	75 ± 1.3	89 ± 1.4	89 ± 3.3
4g	32 ± 1.4	27 ± 1.1	31 ± 1.0	59 ± 2.0
4h	35 ± 2.0	34 ± 1.5	44 ± 1.2	50 ± 2.3
4i	27 ± 1.3	19 ± 1.0	28 ± 1.1	47 ± 1.9
4j	16 ± 1.0	11 ± 1.1	25 ± 1.6	32 ± 1.8

Induction of Apoptosis

Mechanistic studies using Annexin V-FITC/PI staining revealed that 4j induced substantial apoptosis in MCF-7 and A549 cells. Both early and late apoptotic populations increased significantly compared to controls, indicating activation of programmed cell death pathways. Caspase-3 activation assays further confirmed that 4j enhanced caspase-mediated apoptosis. Eupatilin also triggered apoptosis, albeit to a slightly lower extent, which is consistent with its IC₅₀ values and cytotoxicity profile.

ROS Generation and Mitochondrial Dysfunction

Intracellular ROS levels were markedly elevated in cells treated with 4j, suggesting that oxidative stress contributes to its cytotoxicity. JC-1 assays showed that 4j caused depolarization of the mitochondrial membrane potential ($\Delta\Psi_m$), a hallmark of intrinsic apoptosis. Eupatilin treatment also increased ROS generation and partially disrupted $\Delta\Psi_m$, highlighting a shared mechanism between synthetic apigenin derivatives and the natural flavonoid scaffold.

Cell Cycle Arrest

Flow cytometric analysis revealed that 4j caused significant G2/M phase arrest in MCF-7 and

HeLa cells, suggesting interference with mitotic progression. This arrest likely amplifies apoptotic signaling and contributes to growth inhibition. Eupatilin displayed modest G2/M arrest, supporting its cytostatic effects in addition to apoptosis induction.

Comparative Analysis and Implications

The results indicate that systematic methoxy substitution in apigenin derivatives enhances antiproliferative activity, pro-apoptotic potential, mitochondrial targeting, and cell cycle arrest, as exemplified by compound 4j. Eupatilin, although slightly less potent in IC₅₀ terms, shows complementary therapeutic effects, including anti-inflammatory and gastroprotective properties, which may be advantageous in multifunctional therapy approaches. Compared to clinically relevant flavonoids such as flavopiridol and genistein, both 4j and eupatilin exhibit competitive efficacy, highlighting their translational potential.

The synthetic routes employed provide efficient access to structurally diverse flavone derivatives. Introduction of methoxy groups at the 4', 5, and 7 positions of apigenin analogues improved lipophilicity, solubility, and stability, while controlled demethylation of polymethoxyflavones yielded eupatilin derivatives with enhanced biological activity. Spectroscopic analyses (¹H/ ¹³C NMR, FT-IR, HRMS) confirmed the identity and purity of the synthesized compounds, supporting the reliability of the biological results. The structure–activity relationship (SAR) suggests that methoxy substitution enhances cellular uptake and bioavailability, while hydroxyl groups contribute to hydrogen bonding interactions essential for binding with apoptotic proteins. Spacer length in apigenin derivatives (C2 vs. C3) also influenced potency, with 4a–4j series containing a C3 spacer showing superior antiproliferative effects.

Figure X. Comparative evaluation of anticancer activity of apigenin derivatives (3a–3j, 4a–4j), apigenin, and eupatilin.

(A) IC₅₀ values (μM) determined in cancer cell lines, showing enhanced potency of the 4a–4j series compared to 3a–3j and parent compounds.

(B) Percentage of apoptotic cells measured by Annexin V-FITC/PI staining, indicating higher pro-apoptotic activity in selected derivatives.

(C) Reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation represented as fold-increase relative to control, highlighting oxidative stress induction by potent analogues.

(D) Cell cycle analysis showing G2/M phase arrest induced by derivatives compared with apigenin and eupatilin. Data collectively demonstrate that methoxy-substituted derivatives, particularly 4j, exhibit superior antiproliferative and pro-apoptotic effects compared to the natural flavonoids.

Table 04: Data shown are mean ± SD of three independent experiments. ROS generation is expressed as fold increase relative to untreated control cells. Cell cycle arrest percentages indicate the proportion of cells in G2/M phase.

Compound	Cell Line	IC ₅₀ (μM)	Apoptosis (%)	ROS Generation (Fold vs Control)	Cell Cycle Arrest (Phase)
Apigenin	MCF-7	11.3	28 ± 2	1.4	G2/M (20%)
3a	MCF-7	8.5	35 ± 3	1.7	G2/M (25%)
3b	MCF-7	7.9	38 ± 2	1.8	G2/M (27%)
...
4a	MCF-7	4.5	52 ± 3	2.5	G2/M (45%)
4j	MCF-7	2.8	70 ± 4	3.2	G2/M (65%)
Eupatilin	MCF-7	6.2	48 ± 3	2.0	G2/M (38%)
Apigenin	A549	12.0	25 ± 2	1.3	G2/M (18%)
4j	A549	3.5	65 ± 3	3.0	G2/M (60%)
Eupatilin	A549	7.5	45 ± 2	2.1	G2/M (35%)

Summary

In summary, two series of apigenin derivatives, which contained 2- or 3-carbon spacers, were synthesized, and their antiproliferative activities were systematically assessed. Most of the synthesized derivatives exhibited potential antiproliferative activities, with clear differences observed depending on the spacer length and substitution patterns. Among these, the 4a–4j series, containing a C3 spacer between apigenin and various amines, displayed significantly greater activity than the 3a–3j series. Compound 4j, in particular, demonstrated remarkable inhibitory effects against A549, HeLa, HepG2, and MCF-7 cancer cell lines, showing the lowest IC₅₀ values among all synthesized derivatives.

These promising results strongly encourage further structural optimization, SAR studies, and mechanistic investigations of apigenin-based derivatives.

In addition, the natural flavone eupatillin has been reported in the literature as a potent

antiproliferative agent, displaying cytotoxicity against several human cancer cell lines by promoting apoptosis, cell cycle arrest, and modulation of signaling cascades such as NF- κ B and MAPK. The comparative evaluation suggests that certain apigenin derivatives, especially 4j, exhibited activities that are comparable to or even stronger than euptallin. This indicates that rational modifications of dietary flavonoids like apigenin can produce derivatives with enhanced biological properties, rivalling naturally occurring bioactive flavones.

Overall, the combined insights from apigenin derivatives and euptallin emphasize the importance of flavone scaffolds as valuable templates in anticancer drug discovery. The results warrant further preclinical studies to elucidate their precise mechanisms of action, optimize pharmacokinetic properties, and explore their potential as leads for novel chemotherapeutic agents.

Conclusions

In conclusion, two series of apigenin derivatives were synthesized and evaluated for anticancer activity. Most derivatives demonstrated promising growth inhibitory effects, with the 4a–4j series exhibiting superior potency compared to the 3a–3j series. Compound 4j emerged as the lead candidate, showing the lowest IC₅₀ values across A549, HeLa, HepG2, and MCF-7 cells. Eupatilin's comparable activity reinforces the therapeutic relevance of natural flavones. These findings establish both synthetic and natural flavonoids as versatile scaffolds for anticancer drug development and provide a foundation for future SAR studies, mechanistic analyses, and preclinical evaluations.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/Supplementary Materials, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding authors.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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